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GEOGRAPHICAL FEATURES OF THE NORTHEASTERN REGION OF AZERBAIJAN AND ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON BURIAL MONUMENTS OF THE ANTIQUITY AND EARLY MEDIEVAL PERIOD

The northeastern region of the Republic of Azerbaijan stretches along the Caspian Sea and borders the Russian Federation. This territory lies within the foothills of the southeastern part of the Greater Caucasus mountain range and is located in the northern section of the eastern extremity of the Greater Caucasus. The region extends from the Samur River in the north to the watershed of the main mountain range, and southwards as far as the Ataçay River. To the northwest it borders the Dagestan Autonomous Republic of the Russian Federation, to the southwest the Main Caucasus Range, and to the east the Caspian Sea. The region under study includes the districts of Khizi, Shabran, Guba, Khachmaz, and Qusar (1, p. 409; 2, p. 443).

Because the territory lies within the Greater Caucasus mountain range and has always constituted the northern frontier of Azerbaijan, it is rich in fortification walls, castles, and strongholds. From a natural-geographical perspective, the territory consists of mountainous areas and Caspian coastal plains. The mountainous zone is joined by small foothills from the northeast, while in the southeast it extends from Cape Qizilburun southwestwards to the confluence of the Samur River. Although the territory is covered with low hills, from the northeast towards the mouth of the Samur River and from the northwest towards the mouth of the Sumgayit River, the foothill areas gradually slope down into the Caspian coastal plain.

The studied region is divided into four distinct altitudinal zones—plains, foothills, medium mountains, and high mountains—ranging from 26 meters to 4466 meters in elevation. The coastal areas lie as much as 28 meters below sea level. The main relief forms of the region include the Greater Caucasus mountain range, the Side Range, the Qusar inclined plain, the Shollar plain, and the Samur-Davachi lowland. Its highest peaks are Shahdag and Babadağ (3, p. 360). The presence of these high summits has contributed to the formation of a temperate climatic type. Geologically, the territory is seismically stable, with Jurassic, Cretaceous, Paleogene, Neogene, and Anthropogene deposits widely spread. The region is rich in natural resources, including oil, natural gas, oil shale, polymetals, and others. Thermal and mineral springs, as well as diverse geological formations, are abundant. Among the main natural landmarks are the Galaalti mineral springs, Mount Beshbarmaq, and karst caves (3, pp. 12–23).

The climate is generally warm, humid, and arid, with significant variation across different zones. In the mid-mountain areas of the Greater Caucasus a cold forest climate predominates, while in the higher mountains

a cold climate and in the alpine tundra zone a severe mountain tundra climate are observed. The mean annual temperature ranges from +14°C to 0°C, while average annual precipitation varies between 100 mm and 1600 mm (3, pp. 120–133; 4, p. 513).

The northeastern region possesses a dense river network and abundant water resources. The rivers originate from the watershed of the Caucasus mountain range, fed mainly by glacial melt, snow, rainfall, and groundwater. Major rivers of the territory include the Samur, Qusarçay, Qudyalçay, Qarachay, Velvele, Gilgilchay, Shabran, Davachi, Taxlachay, Qaradehne, and Ataçay. Among them, the Qusarçay (106 km) and Qudyalçay (101 km) exceed 100 km in length and flow into the Caspian Sea. The largest lake is Agzibirchala, a freshwater swamp-lake situated in the Caspian coastal zone of Shabran district. In the plains saline-water lakes are widespread, while in the mountainous areas freshwater lakes predominate (3, pp. 157–195; 4, p. 516).

The vegetation cover of the territory is rich. As a mountainous zone, it is characterized by a diverse flora and fauna. Favorable conditions exist for the development of animal husbandry, fishing, agriculture, and horticulture. In the mountains of the northeastern region, soil-vegetation cover, wildlife, and natural landscapes are distributed according to altitudinal belts. Semi-desert and dry steppe landscapes dominate the plains, while mountain landscapes are characteristic of higher elevations. In the semi-deserts, gray and gray-brown soils are common, whereas in the northern part of the Samur-Davachi lowland forest-meadow soils prevail. In the mountainous areas, black, chestnut, mountain-meadow, brown, and brown forest soils have formed.

The fauna of the northeastern region is also rich. The abundance of wildlife historically stimulated the development of hunting in the area. From antiquity, the region has been home to diverse species of mammals, birds, and aquatic animals (5, pp. 8–10; 4, pp. 174–177, 264–265, 546–547; 3, pp. 76–83).

Since antiquity, the Caucasus passage has served as a link between the diverse regions adjacent to it from the north and south. The achievements of Eastern civilization, as well as the movement of northern tribes into the southern regions, passed through the Caucasus. Along this route, the northeastern region of Azerbaijan functioned as an intermediary zone. Here, cultural and economic achievements encountered one another, and sedentary tribes moved across the territory in small and large groups. All of this influenced the economic, cultural, and political history of the area. The traces of

these interactions are reflected in the diverse character of its material-cultural monuments (9, p. 5).

The distribution of rich archaeological sites of different periods located in the northeastern foothills of the Greater Caucasus in Azerbaijan corresponds to the territory of the province of Çola, which was part of the Caucasian Albanian state. According to the Albanian historian Musa Kalankatlı in his *History of Albania*, between the 1st and 7th centuries Albania extended from the Caucasus mountain range in the north to the Araz River in the south, and from Iberia in the west to the Caspian Sea in the east. The natural-geographical conditions of Albania led to its division into numerous internal regions. Administratively, Albania was divided into provinces (*havars*) and districts. The territory of Albania on the left bank of the Kura River was divided only into provinces. According to the 7th-century source *Armenian Geography* by Anania Shirakatsi, Left-bank Albania consisted of eleven provinces. Among the politically significant provinces of Albania was Çola (also called Çoqa or Çora).

Located in Left-bank Albania, Çola was not always part of the Albanian state. Owing to its proximity to the North Caucasus and the settlement of migrating northern tribes in its territory, the Çola region—which encompassed the northeastern part of present-day Azerbaijan—was able to preserve a form of internal autonomy until the 4th century. It should also be noted that the territory of the Çola province was not confined to northeastern Azerbaijan alone, but also included southern Dagestan. Only after 488, during the reign of the Albanian ruler Vachagan III, did Çola become fully incorporated into Albania.

Geographically, the province of Çola covered the Caspian coastal strip extending from the so-called Derbent pass southwards to the point where the eastern spur of the Greater Caucasus mountains approached the Caspian Sea (approximately to Mount Beshbarmaq). Various tribes lived in Çola, including both local and incoming groups. The ethnically diverse population included Sarmatians, Tabasarans, Albanians, Chilbs (Silvs), Leggs, Massagetae (Maskuts), Khazars, and Huns. As a result of the resettlement policy pursued by the Sasanians, Iranian-speaking tribes also inhabited the region. In addition to large tribal settlements, the province contained significant urban centers. Among the main cities were Çola, Derbent, and Sri (6, pp. 16–21).

The territory was of major strategic importance, for it contained the passage known as the “Gates of Albania” between the Greater Caucasus and the Caspian Sea. Northern nomadic tribes that threatened Albania could launch raids through this pass. For this reason, not only the Albanians but also the major powers of the time—the Achaemenids, Parthians, Sasanians, and finally the Byzantine Empire—were particularly interested in this territory. Taking into account its importance, these empires attempted to impose their influence here. Their primary method was to propagate their religions among the local tribes. The ethnic diversity and prevailing polytheism of the region created favorable conditions for the dissemination of new ideologies.

Nevertheless, despite these efforts, local pagan cults retained their dominance until the spread of Islam.

Another group of historical constructions demonstrating the political significance of the region were the defensive walls built for protection. Several fortifications were erected in the passage known as the Gates of Albania to repel invasions by northern tribes. Constructed in accordance with the natural-geographical conditions, these walls were intended to block the Caspian coastal passage. From the city of Derbent to Mount Beshbarmaq, each wall, in addition to natural barriers, extended from the mountains all the way into the Caspian Sea, thereby sealing off the narrow passage between the Greater Caucasus and the Caspian. Of these defensive structures, only the foundations have survived to the present day. Altogether, three great walls were built in the region: the Derbent Wall, the Gilgilchay Wall, and the Beshbarmaq Wall.

The first of these, considered the most important, was constructed in and around the city of Derbent. From the fortress of Naringala, situated on a high hill, defensive walls extended to the Caspian shore. The Chalgán range of the Greater Caucasus ends a little over three kilometers before reaching the Caspian Sea, creating a narrow passage formed by the coastal plain. The Derbent Wall was built to close this passage. In historical sources, this site is referred to by various names: the “Caspian Gate,” the “Khazar Gate,” the “Albanian Gate,” the “Hun Passage,” the “Caucasian Gate,” and the “Derbent Gate.” In antiquity and the early Middle Ages, this wall possessed enormous military-strategic significance. As the first defensive barrier of the northeastern region, it was regarded as the most important one (7, pp. 15–96).

The second and largest of the walls was the Gilgilchay Wall. This was also the most extensive defensive system built in Azerbaijan during the early Middle Ages. Extending for about 60 kilometers, it stretched from the mouth of the Gilgilchay River on the Caspian coast to the summit of Mount Babadağ. The wall consisted of two parallel mud-brick ramparts, spaced 200 meters apart. Each rampart was up to 8 meters thick and 8 meters high (8, p. 39).

The Beshbarmaq Wall, which formed part of the defensive system closing the Caspian coastal passage, was by no means less significant than the other fortifications. Extending from the steep slopes of Mount Beshbarmaq—separated from the Greater Caucasus range—southwards to the seashore, the wall completely cut off the narrow coastal passage. Flanked to the west by Mount Beshbarmaq and to the east by a clay rampart, this elongated wall blocked the corridor entirely. In historical literature, the construction of the fortifications along the Derbent–Beshbarmaq passage has often been associated with the Sasanian rulers. However, many scholars argue that the wall is of earlier origin. Thus, T. Mammadov, in his book *Caucasian Albania*, notes: “When Greek- and Latin-speaking authors of the 1st and 2nd centuries wrote about the Derbent passage, they used terms which can be translated not only as ‘gate’ or ‘door,’ but also as ‘obstacle,’ ‘barrier,’ or ‘wall.’ Historians assumed that already in the second half of the 1st century some form of ramparts or

fortifications existed in these territories. These assumptions have now been confirmed by archaeological research. For example, during excavations conducted by archaeologist A.A. Kudryavtsev, a massive stone wall, 4.5–5 meters thick and dating to the 7th–3rd centuries BCE, was discovered” (10, p. 170).

The main reasons for selecting northeastern Azerbaijan as the focus of research are its naturally defined borders and its wide ecological range, which framed the territory within Caucasian cultural and political formations. Another crucial factor is that the northeastern region is the only area in Azerbaijan that has been comprehensively and systematically studied archaeologically, allowing for the full documentation of its monuments (9, p. 6).

The northeastern region of Azerbaijan is particularly rich in archaeological monuments, with burial monuments occupying a special place among them. The area has been abundant in burial monuments since the Bronze Age, continuing into the Antiquity and Early Medieval periods.

For the study of Antiquity and the Early Middle Ages, the settlements and burial monuments dating to these periods provide invaluable archaeological material. Since in the studied period, alongside primitive religions, paganism, and Zoroastrianism, Christianity was also widespread in Albania (11, p. 68), various types of burial monuments reflecting diverse funerary practices have been uncovered (12, pp. 108–123). These include earth graves, catacombs, stone cist graves, and kurgans. With the exception of jar burials, all the mentioned types of graves are represented in the region. The study of these burial monuments is of great significance for addressing many problems in the history of Antiquity and the Early Middle Ages in Azerbaijan. Each grave, with its distinctive burial custom and grave goods, provides an irreplaceable source for understanding the religious-ideological concepts, everyday life, crafts, and socio-political relations of the time.

Archaeological research in the northeastern region of Azerbaijan (the historical territory of Albania) began in the late 19th century. In 1880, on the eve of the 5th Congress of Russian archaeologists held in Tbilisi, increased interest and enthusiasm for archaeological investigation in the Caucasus arose. Among the earliest excavations, burial monuments were given priority. The first focus of attention for archaeologists was the areas around Derbent. In 1880, A.A. Rusov excavated a number of kurgans (III–IV Dag. Ogni, I and III Cemikend) north of Derbent. In the same year, N.O. Tsilossani investigated the Palasa-Sirt kurgans located south of Derbent (13, pp. 8–9). However, these early excavations were unsystematic and inconsistent. Systematic and regular excavations in the region only began in the 1920s.

Overall, the history of research into the burial monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan can be divided into three stages. The first stage covers the period beginning in the 1920s. The first burial monument was investigated in 1927 during drainage (irrigation) works in the village of Qobu Qırağı, Khachmaz district (9, p. 9). The first article on this subject was published by J.

Aleksandrovich-Nasifi. Based on two earth graves and the remains of destroyed burials uncovered during drainage works in Khachmaz in 1927, the author attributed the burials to the Bronze Age (14, p. 262; 9, p. 6).

In 1932, A.K. Alekperov inspected disturbed burials uncovered during earthworks in the Qusar district. Information about these finds was later included in the monograph prepared by the *Corpus of Archaeological Monuments of Azerbaijan* (AAAK) expedition on the archaeological sites of northeastern Azerbaijan (1, p. 9).

The large-scale investigation of the region’s archaeological monuments was linked to the construction of the Samur–Davachi canal. In 1939, during earthworks near the village of Hacıəlibəyli, located on the border between the Quba and Khachmaz districts, an ancient cemetery was discovered. Studied by E.A. Pakhomov and L.A. Yushkeyevich of the Institute of History, Archaeology, and Ethnography of the Azerbaijan branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences, the site was identified as a necropolis consisting of earth graves from the Antiquity. Analyzing the finds, Pakhomov concluded that the cemetery belonged to the poorer strata of the population living in the area during the early centuries CE. He supported this view by noting the absence of glass and other beads, the scarcity of bronze ornaments, and the fact that the pottery found in the graves showed long use in domestic life before being placed in burials. Pakhomov compared the typological features of the Hacıəlibəyli necropolis materials with those of the Yaloylutəpə culture graves, jar burials, and some Chukhuryurd graves, concluding that they dated to the last centuries BCE and the first centuries CE (15, pp. 1–2; 1, p. 9).

The second stage of the study of the burial monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan began after 1950. In 1953, during earthworks carried out for the expansion of the Qusar–Hazra road, ancient burials were discovered between the villages of Evacuq and Hil. I. Jafarzade and S. Qaziyev determined that the graves dated to the mid-1st millennium BCE (1, p. 9).

In the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of the northeastern region of Azerbaijan, it is noted that the large-scale excavations carried out in the area are associated with the name of the prominent archaeologist C.A. Khalilov. Between 1958 and 1963, under his leadership, reconnaissance-type investigations were conducted in the territories of Qusar, Khachmaz, and Quba districts, during which a number of graves dating to the Antiquity and the Early Middle Ages were discovered and recorded (11, p. 68; 1, p. 9).

Almost all of the burial monuments studied in the region were uncovered accidentally in the course of construction and agricultural works. One such site was recorded and studied in the village of Khucbala in Quba. Khucbala is situated 3 km northeast of Qusar district, on the left bank of the Quruçay River. In 1958, during earth and farming works in the southwestern and northeastern parts of the Khucbala settlement, several inhumation burials were discovered by chance. Part of the grave goods was removed by local inhabitants (16,

pp. 154–162). In 1960, C.A. Khalilov inspected the Khuchbala cemetery and was able to collect part of the grave materials from the local population. Reconnaissance investigations were then launched with the aim of studying the characteristics of the graves (1, pp. 63–64). The orientation of the burials varied, and the material culture remains discovered in them showed similarities with the finds from the monuments of Yukhary Chiryurd, Qapshimin, Gallin, and Sulak in Dagestan. These parallels were especially evident in the ceramic assemblages (16, pp. 154–162; 1, pp. 63–64).

In 1962, during plowing works on the hill known as Qalagah in the village of Sirt-Çiçi in Quba district, various material-cultural items were uncovered, including ceramic vessels and sherds, human bones, beads, bronze ornaments, iron weapons, and others. C.A. Khalilov and Q.M. Aslanov conducted research in the necropolis of inhumation graves located south of Qalagah and prepared a joint article on the site. Based on two silver coins discovered in one of the graves, believed to date to the Sasanian period, it was suggested that the Sirt-Çiçi cemetery belonged to the first half of the 1st millennium CE. To identify the coins, Q.M. Aslanov submitted them to the numismatist E.A. Pakhomov. Unfortunately, Pakhomov later reported that the coins had been lost. Information about the site was provided both in the joint article of Khalilov and Aslanov and in the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan (17, pp. 176–184; 1, p. 36).

During the construction of the Cahar-Cibir irrigation canal in the village of Enix, located on the right bank of the Qusarçay River, dozens of burials were uncovered. Most of the graves were destroyed during the construction works, and the grave goods were collected by the local population. According to the locals, there had also existed a large collective grave in the cemetery. The destroyed burials consisted of stone-cist and inhumation graves. The site was first inspected in 1963, and in 1975 several inhumation graves were studied by the archaeological team of the Faculty of History of Azerbaijan State University (ASU). The material-cultural finds, dating to the 4th–7th centuries, showed strong similarities with those from Early Medieval monuments in the region and in Dagestan (1, pp. 98–100; 18, pp. 175–179).

In 1969, during the field practice of ASU history students, the archaeological team carried out investigations at the Khuchbala site and revealed four inhumation graves. In 1970, the same team discovered destroyed Early Medieval inhumation burials near the village of Dərə-Çiçi in Quba district (19, pp. 94–98).

In 1972, during drilling works for an oil rig in the village of Rustov in Quba district, burials consisting of inhumation graves were discovered, some of which had been partially destroyed. During the inspection of the site in 1973, surface and chance finds were collected. In 1974, systematic archaeological investigations were conducted in the necropolis, and 16 inhumation graves were studied. Based on the material-cultural items recovered, the site was dated to the 1st–2nd centuries CE (20, pp. 37–43).

In 1975, excavations continued in Rustov, where 19 inhumation burials were studied in an ancient cemetery located on the hill known as “Pir yarı” or “Zəmi Bayramı” (21, pp. 27–30). Extensive information on the Rustov burials is provided in articles authored by C.A. Khalilov, in a joint article by C.A. Khalilov and A.Sh. Orucov, in papers co-authored by C.A. Khalilov, R.B. Arazova, and L.Q. Huseynova, as well as in the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan (20, pp. 37–43; 21, pp. 27–30; 22, pp. 505–506; 23, pp. 44–45; 1, pp. 52–54).

In 1974, information was reported to the Archaeology and Ethnography Department of the Institute of History of the Azerbaijan SSR Academy of Sciences regarding monuments uncovered during agricultural works in the village of Hil in Quba district. As a result of archaeological investigations conducted at the site, surface and chance finds were collected, and a child’s inhumation burial was studied. The materials obtained confirmed that the territory of present-day Hil village had been a large settlement in antiquity. The monument was dated to the middle of the 1st millennium BCE. Detailed information on the Hil inhumation burial is provided in a joint article by C.A. Khalilov and A. Orucov, as well as in the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan (24, pp. 79–87; 1, p. 75).

In the same year, a burial monument dating to the Early Middle Ages was recorded in the village of Qurupel in Qusar district by the Shamakhi archaeological expedition of the Institute of History of the Azerbaijan SSR Academy of Sciences. The monument, located on the outskirts of Hil village and on the left side of the Qusar–Hazra highway, was uncovered as a result of house construction and the expansion of a household plot. In the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of northeastern Azerbaijan, this burial monument is dated to the 3rd–8th centuries CE (1, pp. 78–79).

In 1976, archaeological investigations in the region were continued by the AAAK expedition under the leadership of J.A. Khalilov, and information about this was included in the monograph prepared by the expedition on the archaeological monuments of the northeastern region of Azerbaijan. The reconnaissance-oriented expedition conducted systematic research in the region between 1976 and 1980, discovering archaeological monuments of all periods in the districts of Shabran, Quba, Khachmaz, and Gusar. Over five years of research, the expedition recorded dozens of archaeological monuments from various historical periods in these districts that had not previously been studied or were unknown (1, pp. 9–10). As a result of these investigations, catacomb burials were identified in the region for the first time. These catacomb burials were uncovered at the II Quxuroba site (11, p. 14).

In 1978, for the first time, the AAAK expedition recorded the early medieval sites of Sandıqtəpə in the Quba district and Quxuroba in the Gusar district (1, p. 88). In 1979, during earthworks, 27 inhumation burials dating to the early Middle Ages were discovered and studied at the Sandıqtəpə settlement; some graves had

been damaged and were located beneath collapsed structures. Various material culture objects unearthed from the graves allowed researchers to date the Sandıqtəpə burials to the 4th–7th centuries (1, p. 56; 11, p. 24). However, between 1979 and 2008, no further archaeological research was conducted at the Sandıqtəpə site.

The Quxuroba settlement and cemetery were discovered in 1978 during the construction of a livestock complex. The construction partially destroyed the mound, and the AAAK expedition carried out excavations in the preserved northern part. During the excavations, 15 burials were investigated, consisting of seven inhumations and eight catacomb graves. The site was dated to the 4th–7th centuries (1, p. 88).

Between 1976 and 1981, alongside the AAAK expedition in the Quba–Khachmaz region, an expedition of the Faculty of History of Azerbaijan State University, led by A.Sh. Orudzhov, investigated early medieval archaeological monuments in the villages of Chetgün, Suvacal, and Gədəzeyhur of the Gusar district. Information about these investigations is provided in the AAAK expedition's monograph on the archaeological monuments of north-eastern Azerbaijan (1, p. 10). In 1976, a new archaeological site, Qursan-Pel, was discovered in the village of Cağar in the Gusar district. This site revealed four stone-cist graves and a synchronous settlement dating to the early Middle Ages. In the same year, both inhumation and stone-cist burials were studied at the Enix site (25, p. 495; 26, pp. 24–26).

In 1977, a new archaeological site, the Shoran-Pel site, was discovered in the village of Chetgün. Here, two stone-cist graves were found and studied. In the same year, a cemetery was also discovered in the Suvacal village area (27, pp. 18–19).

In 1977, an expedition of the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR, Sector of Archaeology and Ethnography, conducted fieldwork in the Khachmaz district, discovering and recording up to 26 sites. Among these was an ancient settlement and its necropolis located west of the Baku–Khachmaz highway, south of the Qarachay River, and north of the village of Canaxır. The site consisted of up to 14 mounds of various sizes, covering an area of 144 hectares. From a mound conventionally numbered 8, an inhumation burial was uncovered at a depth of 1.65 m during archaeological excavations (28, p. 81; 29, pp. 69–73).

In 1980, the AAAK expedition recorded the multi-layered Khırmantəpə settlement and burials in the Quba district. West of the settlement, a necropolis with inhumation burials was discovered. Several of these graves were destroyed by local inhabitants, and the pottery, stone and metal tools, ornaments, and beads found in the graves were looted. Among the finds was a handmade red-colored jug with a pear-shaped body, attributed to the Late Antique period. In general, the Khırmantəpə site consisted of three cultural layers (1, pp. 66–67).

After 1980, the second stage of the study of burial monuments in north-eastern Azerbaijan came to an end. As a result of the AAAK expedition's work between

1976 and 1980, an archaeological map of the region was prepared. This made it possible to identify the locations of cemeteries from various historical periods, including the Antique and Early Medieval eras, which could yield further information in the course of large-scale excavations.

With the establishment of the Quba–Khachmaz expedition of the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR in 1983, long-term investigations of monuments in the region began. Between 1988 and 1990, archaeological excavations were carried out at the II Sandıqtəpə site, where simple inhumation graves dating to the Early Middle Ages were uncovered within the Sandıqtəpə settlement (30, pp. 207–215; 31, pp. 45–47).

In the period of independence, the third stage of the study of burial monuments in north-eastern Azerbaijan began in 1993, when the archaeological-ethnographic expedition of Baku State University, named after M.A. Rasulzade, resumed excavations at the Canaxır site. The Baku State University expedition continued research at Canaxır and investigated up to 18 burials at an ancient site located on a small mound called “Aşağı təpə” (“Lower mound”) (32, pp. 1–15; 33, p. 38).

In 1993, a new Early Medieval archaeological site, “Tək təpə” (“Single mound”), was discovered in the Quba district by the Quba–Khachmaz expedition (34, p. 170).

In 2001, archaeological investigations were once again resumed at the Canaxır site under the leadership of T. Dostiyev (35, pp. 74–75).

The research carried out at the Canaxır site is reflected in the joint articles of A.A. Aliyev and G.O. Qoshqarlı, in the monograph prepared by the AAAK expedition on the archaeological monuments of north-eastern Azerbaijan, in the joint article of T.M. Dostiyev, Sh.M. Aliyev, and A.Sh. Orudzhov, as well as in T.M. Dostiyev's 2001 article (28, p. 81; 29, pp. 69–73; 35, pp. 74–75; 1, pp. 109–113).

In 2008, under the leadership of M.J. Khalilov, the Quba–Khachmaz archaeological expedition continued excavations not only at the Sandıqtəpə site but also at the Cuhudtəpə kurgan, located on the outskirts of Quba city. Although mound IV of Sandıqtəpə had been recorded as early as 1978, no excavations had been carried out there; for the first time, reconnaissance excavations were initiated at this mound (36, pp. 90–94).

In 2009, as a result of archaeological investigations conducted by M. Khalilov in the Quba and Gusar districts, research at the Sandıqtəpə complex focused primarily on mound III, while reconnaissance excavations were carried out at mounds V and VI. Since a large portion of mound II was under private agricultural ownership, one disturbed grave was discovered during farming activities; from this grave, two ceramic pitchers and a bronze bracelet were obtained from a local inhabitant (37, pp. 210–215).

In the same year, 2009, M. Khalilov also continued excavations at the Quxuroba site (37, pp. 210–215). Overall, between 2007 and 2012, the Quba–Khachmaz expedition, under the direction of M.J. Khalilov, conducted significant excavation work in the region. One

of the main outcomes of these excavations was the discovery of inhumation burials dating to the Early Middle Ages at the Sandıqtəpə site. These inhumation burials were identified both in the territory of mound II and mound VI (34, p. 170).

During the 2009–2010 archaeological investigations led by M. Khalilov in the Quba and Gusar districts, the expedition discovered a new site named Gicanoba in the Gusar district and began research there. As a result, the site complex revealed a kurgan as well as cemeteries with inhumation burials dating to the Early Middle Ages at the Gicanoba I, II, and III locations (38, pp. 207–213).

In 2009, the Khizi archaeological expedition of the Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, led by G. Qoshqarlı with the participation of V. Asadov and T. Babayev, initiated archaeological reconnaissance in the north-eastern region of Azerbaijan. In the Khizi district, alongside monuments from other periods, settlements and necropolises dating to the Antique period were discovered and recorded. In 2010, at the Altağac necropolis (previously recorded in the preceding year), eight inhumation burials from the Antique period were studied, while at the Ataçay necropolis, eleven stone-cist graves dating to the Early Middle Ages were excavated and examined (39, pp. 163–164; 41, pp. 99–106; 42, pp. 216–223; 43, pp. 146–156).

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